

Horizon 2020
Programme

Report of the third transnational workshop (TNWS 3)

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Agris

Agencia pro sa cherca in agricultura
Agenzia regionale per la ricerca in agricoltura
REGIONE AUTONOMA DI SARDEGNA
REGIONE AUTONOMA DELLA SARDEGNA

INRAE

In Extenso

Innovation Croissance

Moredun

Eesti Maaülikool

Estonian University of Life Sciences

AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY

NIBIO

UNIVERSITY OF
DEBRECEN

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement N° 101000471.

5th and 6th of July 2022
Saint-Affrique - France

Sm@RT TNWS3

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OBJECTIVES

3 main objectives were identified for the third transnational workshop (TNWS 3):

- Present Sm@RT project progress and the solutions to needs identified
- Meet face to face and create links and cross-fertilisation
- Visit French sheep farms and showcase innovative solutions

ORGANISATION AND ATTENDEES

The third transnational workshop was the first face to face international meeting. It took place in Saint-Affrique in France, around the French dairy sheep Digifarm. The agenda of the meeting is detailed on the annex 1.

A total of 57 people participated to this third TNWS (25 farmers, 29 researchers and 7 consultants).

TUESDAY 5TH JULY – FARM VISITS

The first day of the TNWS 3 was centred around the technical visits. In the morning, the group visited the French dairy sheep digifarm LaCazotte; in the afternoon, the INRAE experimental farm LaFage and in the evening, the group went to see the Roquefort Societe caves.

La Cazotte – Dairy sheep Digifarm

La Cazotte is a dairy and meat sheep farm, with 465 Lacaune ewes in lactation and 75 Lacaune viande ewes for meat production. The farm is located in the area of the famous AOP French Cheese Roquefort. All the details of the farm are in annex 2.

On arrival on the farm, participants took part in some ice-breaking sessions to show where each delegation were coming from, and which production their farmers are mostly involved in.

Then, they were first welcomed by Christele Droz-Vincent, the headmistress of the high school, followed by Alain Hardy, the head of LaCazotte farm, who presented the farm and its main productions. Finally, France Brebis Laitieres, presented the area and the main challenges faced by sheep and explain how the Roquefort sector is organised.

Then, the participants were split in 3 groups and went to 3 stations on the farm in turns:

- New shed technologies
- New technologies for milking
- New technologies for grazing

The digital technologies presented were:

- Virtual fences
- Weather station
- Connected fences
- Lactocorder TT
- Ultra High Frequency identification tag
- Water mete
- Barn sensors (T°, humidity, CO2)
- Automatic feeder in milking parlour
- Milking Tank dynamic weighing

All the technologies are detailed on the Sm@RT website: <https://smartplatform.network>

Presentations at LaCazotte

INRAe – La Fage experimental farm

La Fage is a dairy and meat sheep farm, with 500 Lacaune ewes in lactation and 280 Romane ewes for meat production. The farm is located in the area of the famous AOP French Cheese Roquefort. All the details of the farm are in annex 3.

The participants were welcomed by Sara Parisot, the head of the research station. She presented main facts about the farms and briefly outlined the research areas covered on the station.

For the visit, participants were split in 4 groups and turned around 3 main stations:

- New technologies for extensive grazing
- New technologies for milking
- New technologies for feeding and inside the shed

The digital technologies presented was:

- Walk over Weighing
- Feeding gates
- Barn sensors
- Weighing and sorting crate
- Gely INRAE tubes

- Proximity loggers and GPS

All the technologies are detailed on the Sm@RT website: <https://smartplatform.network>

Presentations at LaFage

Roquefort Societe Caves visit

The last visit of the day was to the cheese maturing caves of Roquefort. The participants were split in 2 groups to enjoy the visit. At the end of the tour, a degustation of 3 different types of Roquefort was proposed.

WEDNESDAY 6TH JULY - WORKSHOP

The morning of the second day of the TNWS 3 was dedicated to the workshop.

After a welcome by the project coordinator and the French team, the Sm@RT project and its progress was presented to the participants. Next, via a video link, a presentation by Cassandre Matras (Idele) on the dairy and meat sheep sectors in France, was proposed.

Then, participants did an icebreaker session, where each delegation was asked to mime one of the innovations, they had seen the day before.

Norwegian delegation

French delegation

After a coffee break, the participants were split in 3 groups (mixed of delegations) to learn about solutions from the other countries. The solutions presented by countries were:

- Israel: automatic weighing and water consumption in one weighing trough
- Ireland: weighing and sorting crate using LF EID reader and tags
- Norway: GPS collars and Bluetooth tag
- UK: DNA sampling for lamb parentage
- Estonia: hay drying machine
- Italy: individual milk meter

Norway's solution (Lise Grøva)

Italy's solution (Antonello Cannas)

Ireland's solution (Brid McClearn)

During the presentation, each group was encouraged to ask questions and were asked to discuss the positive and negative aspects of the presented technology

The results of these discussions are presented in a table in annex 4.

Finally, participants were asked to vote on all the innovative technologies they had seen during the 2 days.

The preferred technologies were the GPS and the weighing trough, presented respectively by the Norwegian and Israeli partners.

Before leaving, the participants were asked to give feedback on the whole 2 days. The workshop ended after the lunch meal with a friendly 'sweet' coffee, where each delegation brought some specialities from their country to share.

Feedback on the 2 days

'Sweet' coffee

ANNEXES

Annex 1

Transnational workshop 3
4 to 6 July 2022
Saint-Affrique, France

Detailed agenda TNWS 3

Sunday 3 July 2022

All day – Arrival of NFs

- Each NF arrives in Toulouse

Evening - Meal NFs

Meal between the NFs and partners:

Restaurant at 19h45

- Bistrotet à la Une, 10 Rue Labeda, 31000 Toulouse - <https://www.bistroquetalaune.com/menus-carte/>

Night - Toulouse

Each NF book their hotel for the night of 3rd to the 4th of July.

Monday 4 July 2022

10h to 12h - Steering Group meeting

NFs + Partners

Room at Toulouse airport - Hotel NH Toulouse - 15 Rue Charles Lindbergh, 31700 Blagnac

Access

- tramway - Just take the T2 line and stop at the airport stop.
- airport shuttle – from the train station.

12h30 - 14h - Lunch

Lunch NFs + Partners

14h – End of Steering Group meeting (if not finished)

14h30 – 16h – last NF meeting

Laurence and Germain to leave ahead to St Affrique

16h – Meeting at the bus Toulouse airport

Claire and Jean- Marc welcome participants at the airport

Participants (NFs and partners included) go in the bus.

Jean-Marc may stay behind to wait for the 2 Estonian farmers and 2 Norwegian farmers.

Claire will be in the bus (and can liaise with the driver if necessary!)

Departure of bus at 16h45 direction Saint-Affrique

19h – Arrival of participants at Cap Vert Hotel

Bus arrives at the hotel. Participants get their rooms

20h – Evening meal

Meal at the hotel (probably set menu price) paid by each delegation.

Night - Cap vert hotel

Participants sleep at Cap Vert hotel.

Rooms are booked and paid for by each delegation.

Tuesday 5th July 2022

8h – Meeting at the bus

All participants to meet on the hotel car park

Before we go in the bus, NFs give bags and name tags to participants. NFs make their participants sign the signing sheet for the day.

Departure of bus at 8h20

8h30 – Arrival at the Digifarm La Cazotte

5 minutes per delegation: each delegation presents itself near a map of Europe and puts a sticker to show where they've come from. NFs to precise how many farmers, technicians/advisors and researchers they have in their delegation.

Order of delegation:

- UK
- Ireland
- Norway
- Estonia
-
- Italy
- Israël
- France

9h15 - Presentation of the sector

10 minutes + 10 min of translation - Presentation of the sector by France Brebis Laitière

9h40 - Presentation of the farm La Cazotte

10 minutes + 10 min of translation - Presentation by Alain Hardy

10h – Coffee break

10h30 – Stations

	Group L- Lacaune	Group R - Romanov	Group C - Charollais
New shed technologies Germain	10h30	11h	11h30
New technologies for milking Jean-Marc	11h00	11h30	10h30
New technologies for grazing Laurence	11h30	10h30	11h

Group L :

10h30 - New shed technologies

11h - New technologies for milking

11h30 - New technologies for grazing

Group R :

10h30 - New technologies for grazing

11h - New shed technologies

11h30 - New technologies for milking

Group C :

10h30 - New technologies for milking

11h - New technologies for grazing

11h30 - New shed technologies

12h - Pick-Nick lunch

Meal prepared by Cap Vert and taken in the bus for eating in La Cazotte

13h – Departure of the bus for INRAE - La Fage

14h – Arrival in La Fage

15 min + 15 min of translation : Presentation of the farm by Sara Parisot

14h30 - Stations

	Group A - Alpine	Group S - Saanen	Group M – Manech	Group T - Texel
New technologies for extensive grazing (Wow + GPS) Eliel	14h30	14h30	15h30	15h30
New technologies for milking Sara	15h30	16h	14h30	15h
New technologies for feeding and inside the shed (automatic doors, water consumption, environment sensors) Dominique	16h	15h30	15h	14h30

Group A :

14h30 - New technologies for extensive grazing (Wow + GPS)

15h30 - New technologies for milking

16h - New technologies for feeding and inside the shed (automatic doors, water consumption, environment sensors)

Group S :

14h30 - New technologies for extensive grazing (Wow + GPS)

15h30 - New technologies for feeding and inside the shed (automatic doors, water consumption, environment sensors)

16h - New technologies for milking

Group M :

14h30 - New technologies for milking

15h - New technologies for feeding and inside the shed (automatic doors, water consumption, environment sensors)

15h30 - New technologies for extensive grazing (Wow + GPS)

Group T :

14h30 - New technologies for feeding and inside the shed (automatic doors, water consumption, environment sensors)

15h - New technologies for milking

15h30 - New technologies for extensive grazing (Wow + GPS)

16h30 – Coffee break

16h50 – Meeting at the bus

Departure of the bus for the caves de Roquefort at 17h

- 17h30 - Visit of Caves de Roquefort
- 18h30 - 18h40 – Meeting at the bus
- 19h – Arrival at the hotel

20h – Evening meal

Communal meal paid by Idele

Wednesday 6 July 2022

8h30 – Start of Workshop

Room at the Cap Vert Hotel

15 min - Introduction (Claire + all NF in their own language)

20 min - Presentation and state of Sm@RT project (Claire)

30 min – Presentation of the sheep sectors in France (via video-conference)

Ice-breaker : Each delegation mimes one technology/idea from the day before

- 15 min - Instructions + Preparation
- 30 min - Mime (2 minutes per delegation)

10h15 – Coffee Break

30 min: coffee + cakes provided by Cap Vert

10h45 - Workshops

15 min – Explanation & instructions (Claire + Laurence)

2 market place (45 min each)

Participants go to 3 tables at each turn (*or we have presenters who go to the participants groups – to see once we know how many people we have in total*)

Market places :

11h - 11h45 - Market place 1:

- 3 tables : UK, Israël, Estonia (need 3 different technologies to present)
- 10 minutes per table
- Tour 1
 - o 5 min presentation of the techno + testimony (video or NF)
 - o 5 discussion
 - What do you think?
 - What are the +
 - What are the –
- Tour 2, & 3: what do you think? Do you agree with + & -? Any to add?

11h45 - 12h30 Market Place 2 :

- 3 tables : Norway, Ireland, Italy (need 3 different technologies to present)
- 10 minutes per table
- Tour 1
 - o 5 min presentation of the techno + testimony (video or NF)
 - o 5 discussion
 - What do you think?
 - What are the +
 - What are the –
- Tour 2, & 3: what do you think? Do you agree with + & -? Any to add?
- Same 3 groups as earlier

Technologies to present:

Country	Estonia	Israel	France	Hungary	Norway	Ireland	Italy	UK
Technology	Hay drying machine	Weighing trough	none (see day 1)	Absent	GPS & proximity tags	Weighcrate autosorter	Milk meter	Parentage test

Groups:

Group 1: IT + NO + IRE

Group 2: FR

Group 3: ISR + UK + EST

Each NF will present their technology, and we will need another person to translate – so need 2 people per country who can speak English.

12h30 - Vote for the preferred technologies

Each participant has 2 tokens (or stickers) and vote for the 2 technologies that they'd like to install on their farm.

12h45 - Lunch

13h30 – Special Coffee and Good Bye

Each participant/delegation bring a sugary treat of their country to share during coffee, before we all depart.

Claire, Laurence + Jean-Marc to thank everyone + final vote (on flipchart) on the event

14h30 – Departure of bus for Toulouse

Laurence goes in the bus with the participants

18h – Arrival at Toulouse airport

Annex 2 – La Cazotte facts & figures

Location	St-Affrique – Aveyron - France
System type	AOP Roquefort classic system winter milk
Breed	Lacaune
Number of sheep	
Ewe	465 dairy ewes + 75 meat ewes
Ram	18 dairy ram + 4 meat ram
Females lambs	196 dairy + 14 meat
Production	Milk production (and 75 Lacaune ewes in meat production)
Number of lambings	1000
Adults breeding season	May
Youngs breeding season	June
Under land administration	From the Cazotte farm (244 ha of SAU) operation of the Agricultural School of St Affrique: Educational and experimental farm
Forage Grass Base	100 ha
Forage legume base	30ha
Crops	Yes
Hay	Yes (autonomous in normal years)
Grass silage	Yes
grain barley	Yes
field bean	No
Straw	Yes (autonomous in normal years)
number of permanent workers	5.4
number of seasonal workers	0 but 2 or 3 trainees depending on the projects carried out
System	Production of milk based on alfalfa hay, grass silage and corn produced on the farm in the AOP Roquefort system, then based on pasture in the spring.
Sheepfolding	From October for lambing
Power system	Rich base ration (alfalfa hay, ryegrass silage and corn silage) supplemented with dehydrated alfalfa, barley grown on the farm and a commercial nitrogen supplement
Feeding lambs	Just a starter concentrate and mother's milk
Flushing practices	Yes 400g barley + 200g alfalfa (6 to 7 weeks)
Rate (%) of conception	95%

Prolificacy (%)	198% (for AI) 156% on the herd
Abortion rate (%)	3%
Lamb mortality at lambing (%)	14%
Culling rate (%)	30%
Replacement rate (%)	
Breeding scheme	The whole herd is inseminated, then a catch-up fight 10 days later
milking system	2 milkings per day in accordance with the specifications of the AOP
Milk production (l)	For Roquefort Société
Lamb product	Sale of lambs at 1 month, sale of lambs and breeding rams
Marketing et commercialization	Sale of milk for Roquefort society, we also have direct sale at the farm of organic Lacaune lambs, organic Aubrac Genisses, and organic cereals and lentils

Annex 3 - La Fage facts & figures

Location	La Fage dairy sheep
System type	Intensive system AOP Roquefort
Number of sheep	
Ewe	500
Ram	16
Females lambs	190
Production	170 000 l.of milk
Breed	Lacaune
Number of lambings	580
Adults breeding season	July
Youngs breeding season	August
Under land administration	
Pastures	70 ha
Arable lands	97 ha
number of permanent workers	5
number of seasonal workers	2
Feeding	Commercial winter feed based on silage/hay/barley/concentrate Pasture
Lamb feeding	Straw – Complete feed
Flushing practices	Barley
Rate (%) of conception	84
Prolificacy (%)	1.7
Abortion rate (%)	6
Lamb mortality at lambing (%)	5
Culling rate (%)	30
Replacement rate (%)	30
Breeding scheme	Heat synchronization - Animal insemination
milking system	Mechanical milking 2 x 24 stations
Milk production (l)	335 l/ewe
Lamb product	Sold at weaning 17 kg
Marketing et	Cooperative – Société des caves (Lactalis)

commercialization	
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Location	La Fage meat sheep
System type	Integral outdoor on course
Number of sheep	
Ewe	280
Ram	6
Females lambs	80
Production	Meat lamb
Breed	Romane
Number of lambings	260
Adults breeding season	November
Youngs breeding season	November
Under land administration	
Pastures	280 ha
Arable lands	10 ha
number of permanent workers	3
number of seasonal workers	1
Feeding	Winter feed based on silage/hay/barley Range grazing
Lamb feeding	Straw – Complete feed
Rate (%) of conception	70
Prolificacy (%)	1.9
Abortion rate (%)	0
Lamb mortality at lambing (%)	16
Culling rate (%)	30
Replacement rate (%)	30
Breeding scheme	Heat synchronization - Animal insemination
Lamb product	Sold at 37 kg
Sale of selected live animals	80
Marketing et commercialization	Cooperative – OS Romane

Annex 4 - Results from the workshop discussions:

Technology presented	What do you think?	Positive	Negative
Norway: GPS and proximity tags	Good, especially for extensive farming, of if used with a tag. It may be stolen.	Finding your animals Predator, alarms in real time Managing grazing ground	Cost Open access to data
Ireland: EID weigh crate and autosorter	Can be combined with other tools (eg clamp, turnover crate) Could be adapted for pregnancy scanning Can use box to add additional information (eg BCS) Could be used outside if air compressor + electricity supply Useful for meat and dairy systems Could add a tool to mark the animal in the crate	Time saving Labour saving Meat system drafting Suitable for manual use too 1 person use	Cost Not for individuals, not ideal for large groups Not easy to move, share (would need a portable air compressor) Supplier is in NZ so difficult to get assistance.
Italy: Milk meter	Useful Fundamental	Selection and culling Feeding based on production Health control Pregnancy diagnosis	Calibration Cost Reliability Software connectivity with other systems
Estonia: hay drier	Nice idea, maybe also appropriate in Mediterranean conditions	Consistent quality Energy efficiency Ease of access to feed Ameliorate climate change	Feed efficiency unquantified Energy cost Space availability/requirement DM minimum?
UK: DNA parentage	Good for breeding Accurate data	Accurate data Assessing ram performance Data for breeding programme Don't have to tag lambs at birth Labour saving at lambing	Maybe not commercial Cross border issues Cost of service
Israel: weighing trough	Interesting Very nice, modify to feed Very advanced Combine with sorting gate	Alerts Ability to get insight from different sources Real time weight Identification of individual problems Applicable to dairy as well	Cost Only indoor system

